

THE IMAGE OF ORIENTAL SCHOLARS IN CHINGIZ

AKHMAROV'S WORK

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Since the 1940s of the last century, Uzbek fine art has been accompanied by references to figures of mature historical figures and thinkers, as well as social criticism of the history of the former Soviet Union. On the one hand, the policy of preserving the cohesion of Soviet society in the 1940s and 1960s, taking into account the growing national and cultural identity trends in the republics, the central government declared the advanced cultural heritage of the people of the republic as universal wealth. historical figures who tried to show that the principles of cultural policy are based on international values and whose ideas correspond to the principles of official national policy are distinguished from the cultural heritage. For example, great poets and poets such as Alisher Navoi in Uzbekistan, Shota Rustaveli in Georgia, Nizamiy Ganjavi in Azerbaijan, Firdavsi and Rudaki in Tajikistan have been widely recognized and widely distributed in the country[1].

In the 1940s, the appeal of artists to the creative heritage of Alisher Navoi creates two opposite currents in the artistic consciousness of artists. The first is the movement led by V. Kaydalov, who was the majority of supporters of social realism, opposed to formalism and decoratism. In 1940, the artist created a chronometric portrait of Alisher Navoi and was awarded the republican prize for the "correct and truthful interpretation" of the image of the medieval poet. The initiator of the second trend is Chingiz Akhmarov, the author of a new artistic lyrical-romantic interpretation that reflects the history and national cultural heritage. The rich cultural heritage of the Uzbek people that it is widely manifested in a series of certain images in Ch. Akhmarov's work. He described of rulers and

poets, statesmen and generals, architects and famous scientists, sages and medieval Eastern beauties. It is one of the main themes of Ch. Akhmarov's work, and most of them were created in 1961-1962. Sharof Rashidov, who became the head of the republic in 1959, was the main reason for the partial creative freedom given to artists and intellectuals during this period.

It was during this period that an atmosphere of tolerance for the new interpretation of artistic and literary figures was created in Uzbekistan, and A. Navoi Theater (now Alisher Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater). The essence of the search for national identity from the medieval Eastern cultural traditions, which was first reflected in the mural paintings created by Ch. Akhmarov, showed its buds.

Chingiz Akhmarov's interpretation of the image of Alisher Navoi occupies a central place in his work, his lyrical-epic works are distinguished by the artist's lyrical-romantic intonation and elegant colors from the interpretation of other historical figures of the past. In 1968, on the occasion of the 525th anniversary of the poet Ch. Akhmarov created works dedicated to different stages of the poet's life. These are "Navoi in childhood" (1965. Fabric, tempera. 100x100 cm. #200. Fund of the Academy of Arts.) "Yosh Navoi" (1968. fabric, tempera. 110x110 cm. Tashkent. State Art Museum of Uzbekistan), "Alisher Navoi with students" (1968. Fabric, tempera. 250x140 cm. Tashkent. State Art Museum of Uzbekistan), "The Poet and Roses" (1968. Sketch of a majestic mural. Cardboard, tempera. 53x49 cm.[2]. In particular, in the work "Poet and Roses" Alisher Navoi's aging state is expressed, and through a psychological approach to the image, it is possible to observe the state of exhaustion and memory sandsash (nostalgia).

At the beginning of the years of 1960s, he actively worked on creating the image of Mirzo Ulug'bek, including the works of illustrations for the book for the drama "Mirzo Ulug'bek" by the poet Maqsud Shaykhzoda (1962), "The Star of Ulug'bek" by the director Latif Fayziyev (1963-1964 years) as a costume artist for the film, in 1964-1965 he decorated the interior of the Ulug'bek Museum in Samarkand with huge panels, and in 1970 Ulug'bek's picture in the scene of the

palace banquet in these murals is reflected in the interior of the “Yulduz” cafe. In the following years Ch. Akhmarov returns to the image of Ulug'bek and now he is not interested in the content of the story, perhaps he focuses on the specifics of the psychological state of the scientist, ruler and poetess. It is noticeable that there is a desire to somehow “humanize” the historical person whose life and work was bright but tragic[3]. But taking into account that the ruler and astrologer lived 53 years in the “Portrait of Ulugbek” created 20 years later, that is, in 1993, perhaps he depicted the last years of Ulugbek's rule? The strong look of the ruler-scientist, reflected in this portrait, testifies to the events of Ulugbek's difficult life.

In 1980 the years Chingiz Akhmarov creates sketches for the counter in the interior of the Palace of Gas Workers in Bukhara, in which he creates the images of Ibn Sina and Al-Khwarizmi. For example, in the easel portrait of Ibn Sina, the image of the great scientist and healer is in a slightly simpler form of a bowl and a vial? Illustrated with an embryo inside. To recognize the figure of Mathematician Al-Khorazmi, he depicts him holding triangular or circular geometric shapes, Ch. Akhmarov painted the background of these portraits using deep blue colors and Mayan architectural decorations. The portrait "Beruni and Ibn Sina" made in 1981 (fabric, tempera. 115x115 cm. Fund of the Academy of Arts.) skillfully depicts the state of two scientists having a scientific discussion.

As a conclusion, we can state that Chining Akhmarov's works of the great scholars of the East: Ibn Sina, Al-Khorazmi, Al-Beruni, Alisher Navoi, Mirzo Ulug'bek and others... served as an artistic qualification school for artists interested in historical subjects after him and may become classic examples for the generation of young artists in the understanding of historical, national identity.

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